

प्रतिपित्सा Pratipitsā

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प्रधानसम्पादकः
प्रो. राजारामशुक्लः

वैदिकदर्शनविभागः
काशीहिन्दूविश्वविद्यालयः वाराणसी

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परामर्शदातृमण्डलम्

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डॉ. शशिकान्तद्विवेदी ● डॉ. सरोजकुमारपाढी

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अन्तःसिद्धान्तीयचिन्तनोन्मुखाः विवादरहिताश्च शोधलेखाः प्रकाश्यन्ते।
भाषा संस्कृतं, हिन्दी, आङ्गली चानुमता-सं.)

प्रकाशकः

वैदिकदर्शनविभागः

संस्कृतविद्याधर्मविज्ञानसङ्घायः

काशीहिन्दूविश्वविद्यालयः, वाराणसी

E-mail - pratipitsavdbhu@gmail.com

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मुद्रकः

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इन्दिरानगर, चितईपुर

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Right View : A Theravāda Analysis

Ramesh Prasad

As we know that *Gautama Siddhārtha* was enlightened through his right view on **Vaisākha Pūrṇimā** and after comprehension of right view he avoided the theory of Eternalism (*sāśvatavāda*) and Annihilationism (*ucchevāda*) because both are unreal and do not help to get rid of suffering. For the cessation of suffering one should have the right view because without it one cannot know the real nature of life, i.e., impermanent (*anicca*), subject to suffering (*dukkha*) and substanceless (*anatta*). Therefore a being to know the real nature of life and to get rid of suffering makes an effort to cultivate right view.

The word **Right View** means to understand things as they really are and not as they appear to be. It is not indulging in the speculation or bewildering in the darkness of ignorance. It is the application of Insight to the five aggregates (*Pañcakkhandhas*¹) of clinging and understanding their true nature, i.e., understanding oneself. It is self examination and self observation. It is light of wisdom. Thus one who is in possession of right view gets perfect intuitive wisdom and perceives all the five aggregates as impermanent, subject to suffering and substanceless.² Knowing so he cuts down the attachment from its roots and makes the consciousness free from all attachments and thus, attains **Nibbāna**, i.e., *Summum bonum* of life.

This right view may be understood with the help of the following five steps:

Step 1: Knowing the root (*mūla*) and the action (*kamma*)

Step 2: Knowing the fourfold food (*āhāra*)

Step 3: Knowing the four noble truths (*cattāri ariyasaccāni*)

Step 4: Knowing the law of dependent origination (*paṭiccasamuppāda*)

Step 5: Knowing the fourfold canker (*āsava*)

Step 1:

The right view consists in knowing the three immoral roots (*akusalamūla*) and the ten types of immoral actions (*akusalakamma*) and also the three types of moral roots (*kusala-mūla*) and the ten types of moral actions (*kusala-kamma*). He fully understands the three types of physical misconduct as killing (*pāṇātipāto*), stealing (*adinnādānam*) and committing adultery (*kāmesu micchācāro*), four kinds of vocal misconduct as telling lie (*musāvādo*), slandering (*pisuṇāvācā*), using harsh speech (*pharusāvācā*), and indulging in ignoble gossip (*samphappalāpo*) and three kinds of mental misdeeds known as covetousness (*abhijjhā*), ill-will (*byāpādo*) and wrong view (*micchādiṭṭhi*). He further understands that these immoral actions are rooted in greed (*lobha*), hatred (*dosa*) and ignorance (*moha*). Here *lobha* is the name of the initial desire to take the things which belong to someone else, *dosa* is the desire to harm others and *moha* is the name of ignorance. These three immoral roots have a way of natural combination. *Lobha* and *moha* are friends and they function together. *Dosa* and *moha* are also friends who can also function together. *Moha* may remain alone. There is no possibility of functioning of all these three roots together. With the association of these immoral roots there is the arising of immoral actions which are above mentioned ten in number. He comprehends the three types of physical moral actions as refraining from killing (*pāṇātipātā veramaṇī*), refraining from stealing (*adinnādānā veramaṇī*) and refraining from committing adultery (*kāmesu micchācārā veramaṇī*); four kinds of vocal moral actions as refraining from false speech (*musāvādā veramaṇī*), refraining from slanderous speech (*pisuṇāya vācāya veramaṇī*), refraining from harsh speech (*pharusāya vācāya veramaṇī*) and refraining from useless gossip (*samphappalāpā veramaṇī*) and three kinds of mental moral actions as the absence of covetousness (*anabhijjhā*), absence of ill-will (*abyāpāda*) and the absence of wrong view (*sammādiṭṭhi*). He also understands that these moral actions are rooted in sacrifice (*alobha*), friendliness (*adosa*) and right understanding (*amoha*). All the three moral roots are friendly to each other. They may lead together or sometimes *amoha* remains absent in some cases. With the association of these moral roots there arise above said ten types of moral actions. Thus, understanding immoral actions,

immoral roots, moral actions and moral roots he creates detachment from worldly things and having got rid of ignorance, having made knowledge arise he gets rid of suffering in this life.³

Step 2:

Turning to know the right view we enter into its second step which is about knowing the food (**Āhāra**), origin of food (*āhāra-samudaya*), cessation of food (*āhāra-nirodha*) and the path leading to the cessation of food (*āhāranirodhagāminī-paṭipadā*). In generic sense *āhāra* is food. What one eats is *āhāra*. But in technical sense *āhāra* means nourishment. It is a quality of nourishing the beings. The food which we eat is not *āhāra* but the quality of its nourishing is *āhāra*.⁴ It is of four types, i.e., material food, coarse or fine (*kabalīkāra-āhāra*), sense impingement (*phassa-āhāra*), volition (*manosañcetanā-āhāra*) and consciousness (*viññāṇa-āhāra*). The *kabalīkāra-āhāra* refers to the gross food. One takes gross food morsel by morsel. In this sense it is called *kabalīkāra-āhāra*. *Phassa* means touch. This may appear either through the body or speech. In our practical life we see a baby sleeping on the bed. All of a sudden the baby starts crying. The mother simply pats with her hands; it is mere touch of the hand of the mother and the body of the baby. This touch generates nourishment and the baby again starts sleeping. We also see that the hens lay eggs and remains touching the eggs with their legs and feathers, the eggs receive nourishment and turn into small babies. In this way *phassa* as *āhāra* should be understood. *Manosañcetanā* is the name of volition. It may be seen in worldly as well as in spiritual life. A man practices *Sādhanā*, he follows the moral precepts, practices meditations and realizes right understanding and nourishes a pious volition for attainment of *Nibbāna*. He goes through the rigorous practices in the hope of getting a peaceful state known as *Nibbāna*. This pious volition is the example of *manosañcetanā-āhāra*. *Viññāṇa* means consciousness. It is regarded as food or nourishment. A man does moral and immoral activities; he accumulates the resultant of such activities. Such resultants go on accumulating on the consciousness and as a stream or flow pass from one state of existence to another. With such accumulation the man appears in the womb of mother, here is the appearance of one resultant consciousness which we name *paṭisandhi* or birth consciousness. This birth consciousness is *viññāṇa*. It is nourished by itself with the accumulation of the moral and immoral

consciousness. It is in this sense *viññāna* is regarded as *āhāra*. These four types of nourishment arise due to desire. Thus one who is in possession of right view understands that desire (*taṇhā*) is the cause of uprising of *āhāra*. He also understands the fact that the *āhāras* appear due to attachment, then, by uprooting the attachment the origin of *āhāra* may be checked. This cessation may be possible by following a path, i.e., the noble eightfold path.⁵

Step 3:

The third step towards understanding the right view consists in having a right comprehension of the four noble truths. He understands suffering (*dukkha*), its uprising (*dukkha-samudaya*), its cessation (*dukkha-nirodha*) and the path leading to its cessation (*dukkhanirodhagāminīpaṭipadā*). He comprehends that birth is suffering; ageing is suffering; death is suffering; sorrow, lamentation, pain, grief and despair are suffering; association with the unloved is suffering; separation from the loved is suffering; not to get what one wants is suffering; in short, the five aggregates of clinging is suffering⁶. He understands that desire or craving is the cause of uprising of suffering. This craving appears in three ways, namely, craving for sense pleasures (*kāma-taṇhā*), craving for continued existence or becoming (*bhava-taṇhā*) and craving for non-existence or self-annihilation (*vibhava-taṇhā*)⁷. He, further, knows that the cessation of craving is the cessation of suffering. Since suffering is generated or caused by some reasons, there is a possibility of putting the suffering to an end. The end of suffering is met by the utter fading away and cessation of that very craving, giving it up, renouncing it, emancipation from it, detachment from it⁸. That is the state of *Nibbāna*⁹. This suffering can be stopped by following the Noble Eightfold Path¹⁰, i.e., right view, right resolution, right speech, right action, right livelihood, right effort, right mindfulness and right concentration. By knowing the fourfold noble truth and by following the eightfold path sincerely and devotedly he succeeds in knowing truly right and wrong, moral and immoral, profitable and harmful things and thereby, gives up craving and attachment for them.

Step 4:

Through the right view one understands that suffering is there due to certain conditions and it is dependent on them. In other words he comprehends the law of dependent origination (*paṭīccasamuppāda*)¹¹

which explains that there is nothing like self-independent entity. Everything comes into being depending on the other. When one exists, there is the possibility of existence of the other; when one does not exist the possibility of existence of others is not seen. In the background, there are twelve links which make the wheel of becoming (*bhavacakka*) revolving. They exist depending upon each other. The twelve links are: ignorance (*avijjā*), activities (*saṅkhāra*), birth-consciousness (*viññāna*), mind and matter (*nāma-rūpa*), six senses (*saḷāyatana*), touch (*phassa*), feeling (*vedanā*), desire (*taṇhā*), craving (*upādāna*), becoming (*bhava*), birth (*jāti*) and decay and death (*jarāmaraṇa*). With the understanding of the links, he knows the circle of existence. The first two links (*avijjā* and *saṅkhāra*) belong to the past. The last two links (*jāti* and *jarāmarāṇa*) belong to the future. The remaining eight links in the middle belong to the present state of life. He also comprehends that belonging to the past life, there is the existence of the present one and depending on the present one, there is the possibility of arising of the future life. It is in this way; the circle of existence goes on revolving and exhibits the *Samsāra* as a fact of life.

Step 5:

In the end the right view consists in understanding the fourfold Canker (*Āsava*) viz. the canker of sense desire (*kāmāsava*), the canker of desiring eternal existence (*bhavāsava*), the canker of wrong view (*ditṭhāsava*), and the canker of ignorance (*avijjāsava*). Here, *kāmāsava* is the desire of dominating nature to enjoy the pleasure of the sense. *Bhavāsava* refers to the passionate desire for maintaining the existence or for rebirth in the plains of form and formlessness. *Ditṭhāsava* is such type of polluting factor through which a man holds fastidiously a wrong notion irrespective of any consideration. Not knowing the four noble truths, not knowing the effect of *kamma* in the past, present and future, not knowing the law of dependent origination, etc. is called *avijjāsava*. He comprehends¹² that ignorance is the cause of the origin of canker, cessation of ignorance is the cessation of canker and the Noble Eightfold Path leads to its cessation. Thus comprehending the canker, its origin and the path leading to its cessation, he gets rid of attachment, anger (*paṭigha*), notion of I-ness and ignorance, having made the knowledge arise he becomes an end maker of suffering in this very life.

Thus the comprehension of the right view depends upon having the right understanding of the *dhammas* as stated above under five steps. This right understanding makes the vision crystal clear to view the things as they really are. There is penetration into the nature of reality. The reality becomes a reliable truth. In the light of such right understanding the *yogāvacara* clearly understands that everything is impermanent, subject to suffering and substanceless. Knowing it, he curtails his attachment towards the worldly things and reaches a desireless stage. This stage is called *Nibbāna*, a state of unutterable eternal bliss.

References:

1. Pañcakkhandhas are rūpakkhandha (matter-aggregate), vedanākkhandha (feeling-aggregate), saññākkhandha (perception-aggregate), sañkhārakkhandha (activity-aggregate) and viññāṇakkhandha (consciousness-aggregate).
2. "Paññā, mahārāja, uppajjamānā avijjandhakāraṃ vidhameti, vijjohāsāṃ janeti, ñāṇālokaṃ vidamseti, ariyasaccāni pākaṭāni karoti. Tato yogāvacarō aniccaṃ ti vā dukkhaṃ ti vā anattā ti vā sammappaññāya passati."
- *Milindapañho*, p.37, *Vipassanā Research Institute (VRI)*, Vol.81, *Igatpuri*, 1998
3. Yato kho, āvuso, ariyasāvako evaṃ akusalaṃ pajānāti, evaṃ akusalamūlaṃ pajānāti, evaṃ kusalaṃ pajānāti, evaṃ kusalamūlaṃ pajānāti, so sabbaso rāgānusayaṃ pahāya, paṭighānusayaṃ paṭivinodetvā asmī ti diṭṭhimānānusayaṃ sumūhanitvā, avijjāṃ pahāya vijjāṃ uppādetvā, diṭṭheva dhamme dukkhassantakaro hoti- ettāvataṃ pi kho, āvuso, ariyasāvako sammādiṭṭhi hoti, ujugatāssa diṭṭhi, dhamme aveccappasādena samannāgato, āgato imaṃ saddhammanti.
- *Majjhimanikāyo I, Sammādiṭṭhisuttaṃ*, p.60, *VRI*, Vol.12, *Igatpuri*, 1998
4. Tattha āharatīti āhārapaccayasāṅkhātena uppattiyā, ṭhitiyā vā paccayabhāvena attano phalaṃ āneti nibbatteti pavatteti cāti attho. - *Visuddhimagga-Mahāṭīkā I*, p.388, *VRI*, Vol. 139
5. "Yato kho, āvuso, ariyasāvako āhāraṃ ca pajānāti, āhārasamudayaṃ ca pajānāti, āhāranirodhaṃ ca pajānāti, āhāranirodhagāminipaṭipadaṃ ca pajānāti- ettāvataṃ pi kho, āvuso, ariyasāvako sammādiṭṭhi hoti." - *Majjhimanikāyo I, Sammādiṭṭhisuttaṃ*, p.60, *VRI*, Vol.12, *Igatpuri*, 1998.
6. "Jāti pi dukkhā, jarā pi dukkhā, maraṇaṃ pi dukkhā, sokaparidevadukkhadomanassupāyāsā pi dukkhā, appiyehi sampayogo pi dukkho, piyehi vippayogo pi dukkho, yampiccharaṃ na labhati taṃ pi dukkhaṃ, saṅkhittena pañcupādānakkandhā pi dukkhā," - *Ibid.*, p.61

7. Yāyaṃ taṇhā ponobbhaviḱā nandīrāgasahagatā tatratatrābhinandinī, seyyathidaṃ, kāmatanḱhā, bhavatanḱhā, vibhavatanḱhā. - *Mahāvaggo, p.14, VRI, Vol.89, Igatpuri, 1998*
8. Idaṃ kho pana, bhikkhave, dukkhanirodhaṃ ariyasaccaṃ - yo tassā yeva taṇhāya asesavirāganirodho cāgo paṭinissaggo mutti anālayo. - *Ibid.*
9. Paramatthato hi dukkhanirodho ariyasaccanti nibbānaṃ vuccati. - *Visuddhimaggo II, p. 137, VRI, Vol.138, Igatpuri, 1998*
10. Idaṃ kho pana, bhikkhave, dukkhanirodhagāminīpaṭipadā-ariyasaccaṃ - ayameva ariyo aṭṭhaṅgiko maggo, seyyathidaṃ-sammādiṭṭhi sammāsaṅkappo sammāvācā sammākammanto sammā ājīvo sammāvāyāmo sammāsati sammāsamādhi. - *Mahāvaggo, p.14, VRI, Vol.89, Igatpuri, 1998*
11. Avijjāpaccayā saṅkhārā, saṅkhārapaccayā viññāṇaṃ, viññāṇapaccayā nāmarūpaṃ, nāmarūpapaccayā saḱāyatanāṃ, saḱāyatanapaccayā phasso, phassapaccayā vedanā, vedanāpaccayā taṇhā, taṇhāpaccayā upādānaṃ, upādānapaccayā bhavo, bhavapaccayā jāti, jātipaccayā jarāmaṇaṃ sokaparidevadukkhadomanassupāyāsā sambhavanti-evametassa kevalassa dukkhakkhandhassa samudayo hoti. - *Ibid., pp.1,2*
12. Yato kho, āvuso, ariyasāvako āsavaṃ ca pajānāti, āsavasamudayaṃ ca pajānāti, āsavanirodhaṃ ca pajānāti, āsavanirodhagāminīṃ paṭipadaṃ ca pajānāti, so sabbaso rāgānusayaṃ pahāya, paṭighānusayaṃ paṭivinodetvā, asmī ti diṭṭhimānānusayaṃ samūhanitvā, avijjaṃ pahāya vijjaṃ uppādetvā, diṭṭheva dhamme dukkhassantakaro hoti-Ettāvataṃ pi kho, āvuso, ariyasāvako sammādiṭṭhi hoti, ujugatāssa diṭṭhi, dhamme aveccappasādena samannāgato, āgato imaṃ saddhammanti. - *Majjhimanikāyo I, Sammādiṭṭhisuttaṃ, p.70, VRI, Vol.12, Igatpuri, 1998*